

Report of the Scientific and Training Conference “The Common Agricultural Policy after 2022, with particular emphasis on the strategic plans of the European Union Member States”

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Abstract

L'objectif de la conférence scientifique et de formation "La politique agricole commune après 2022, avec un accent particulier sur les plans stratégiques des États membres de l'Union européenne" était de discuter du plan stratégique polonais pour la politique agricole commune (PAC) et des défis de l'agriculture européenne. La discussion a abouti à la conclusion que la nouvelle politique agricole commune met fortement l'accent sur la nécessité de protéger l'environnement et de lutter contre le changement climatique. Cela se traduit par le montant des fonds alloués aux écoschémas. Il faut s'attendre à ce que la participation à de nombreux programmes d'aide soit conditionnée au respect d'un certain nombre d'exigences dites "environnementales".

Ziel der Wissenschafts- und Ausbildungskonferenz "Die Gemeinsame Agrarpolitik nach 2022, unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der Strategiepläne der EU-Mitgliedstaaten" war es, den polnischen Strategieplan für die Gemeinsame Agrarpolitik (GAP) und die Herausforderungen für die europäische Landwirtschaft zu diskutieren. Das Ergebnis der Diskussion war die Schlußfolgerung, dass die neue Gemeinsame Agrarpolitik die Notwendigkeit des Umweltschutzes und der Bekämpfung des Klimawandels stark betont. Dies zeigt sich auch in der Höhe der für die Ökoregime vorgesehenen Mittel. Es ist zu erwarten, dass die Teilnahme an zahlreichen Hilfsprogrammen an die Erfüllung einer Reihe von so genannten "Umwelt"-Anforderungen geknüpft sein wird.

Conference report

The aim of the Scientific and Training Conference “The Common Agricultural Policy after 2022, with particular emphasis on the strategic plans of the European Union Member States” was to discuss the Polish strategic plan for the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and the challenges of European agriculture. The outcome of the discussion was the conclusion that the new Common Agricultural Policy strongly emphasises the need to protect the environment and to combat climate change. This can be seen in the amount of funds earmarked for ecoschemes. It is to be expected that participation in numerous aid programmes will be conditional on meeting a number of so-called "environmental" requirements.

On 10 January 2023, a Scientific and Training Conference entitled The Common Agricultural Policy after 2022 with particular reference to the strategic plans of the European Union Member States was

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held. The aim of the conference was to discuss the Polish strategic plan for the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and the challenges of European agriculture.

As a result of the European Commission's approval of 28 strategic plans prepared by all EU Member States (Belgium prepared two plans), the new CAP for the period 2023 - 2027 came into force on 1 January 2023. In addition to the most important element of the CAP, i.e. direct payments, a strong emphasis was placed on environmental protection and combating climate change - as many as four out of ten cross-cutting objectives were devoted to these issues.

The conference was officially opened by Professor Dr. Hab. Tomasz Nieborak, Dean of the Faculty of Law and Administration of the Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan, as well as Janusz Wojciechowski European Commissioner for Agriculture, Janusz Kowalski Deputy Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development, Geoff Whittaker the President of European Council for Rural Law and Professor Dr. Roman Budzinowski President of the Management Board of the Polish Association of Agricultural Lawyers, Head of the Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Law at the University of Adam Mickiewicz in Poznan.

The first session, moderated by Professor UAM Dr.hab. Aneta Suchoń consisted of an questions and answers addressed to the European Commissioner for Agriculture - Janusz Wojciechowski, about the new CAP for the period 2023 – 2027. As announced by Janusz Wojciechowski, European Commissioner for Agriculture and Rural Development, the budget of the new CAP is to amount to EUR 264 billion, of which EUR 25 billion has been allocated to Poland. As the Commissioner emphasised, this amounts to approximately PLN 8,000 per hectare and over PLN 100,000 for a statistical Polish farm. Among the challenges to be addressed by the new agricultural policy, the Commissioner pointed first of all to the problem of generational replacement and the decline in the number of farms. In Europe, 3 million farms have disappeared from 12 million to 9 million in one decade. Interestingly, statistics show that Poland has some of the youngest farmers in the EU - the average age in the country is over 50 (the European average is 57).

Until now, Polish farmers have expressed numerous doubts about the obligations which are to be met in order to obtain EU funds. These concerns were addressed by Janusz Wojciechowski, European Commissioner for Agriculture and Rural Development, who indicated that the new CAP is an opportunity for Polish farmers rather than a threat. As he pointed out - Agriculture cannot be about exploiting the land at any price, farmers know this, they do not need to be persuaded to do so, to respect the land. In particular, the Commissioner mentioned two main eco-schemes as an opportunity for farmers in Poland - animal welfare and carbon farming.

Ecoschemes are a new type of direct payment for the implementation of practices beneficial for the environment and climate that go beyond the basic requirements set out in conditionality.

According to the Commissioner, Poland will become the European leader when it comes to support for animal welfare, with almost EUR 2 billion for farmers who voluntarily introduce higher standards on their farms. Among the practices to be rewarded are summer grazing, more space in animal buildings, the use of straw bedding and longer stays for animals with their mothers.

The Commissioner then discussed the second eco-scheme - carbon farming. This consists of a set of good practices that aim to reduce carbon emissions and increase carbon retention in the soil. Actions

that make up the ecoscheme and will be rewarded under the CAP include straw-soil mixing, no-till and increased crop rotation. The Commissioner described these as good for the environment, as well as for the farmers themselves.

Farmers should carefully read the rules for the allocation of funds under ecoschemes, as 2/3 of the budget for production-linked direct payments is allocated to livestock production and 25% of the total direct payment budget is allocated to ecoschemes, including carbon farming. As officials from Polish Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development pointed out, the new agricultural policy implies a greater emphasis on the conditionality mechanism for payments.

Asked about the aspects of the CAP that should be improved, Commissioner Wojciechowski first pointed to the need to improve crisis management in agriculture at EU level. In his opinion, instruments should be put in place to ensure that challenges such as natural disasters or animal diseases (ASF, avian influenza) can be dealt with quickly and effectively at EU level.

The second aspect requiring more intensive action is the lack of successor farmers, which is a huge problem for European agriculture as a whole. The measure included in the new CAP to encourage a new generation of farmers is support for young farmers. Its beneficiary is to be an adult natural person, under 40 years of age, who will set up on an agricultural holding for the first time. The support, paid out in two instalments, is to amount to 200 000 PLN.

In a discussion devoted to the Polish Strategic Plan, Wiktor Szmulewicz (President of the National Council of Agricultural Chambers) noted that large commodity farms are currently considering whether to make use of the aid programmes included in the new CAP. According to the president, the implementation of a number of measures included in the strategic plan will be associated with a decrease in yields. Therefore, if the financial support received is inadequate to the losses incurred, some farmers will abandon the programmes postponed under the CAP. Another risk highlighted by the representative of the National Council of Agricultural Chambers is the disproportion between the difficulty of implementing individual ecoschemes. Consequently, if the majority of producers perform an ecoscheme that is easy to implement, then the funds allocated per hectare may be less than expected.

During the discussion, attention was also drawn to the drastically decreasing number of livestock farms. In Poland, the number of pig farms has fallen by as much as 70% compared to 2014. Similarly, in the milk market - the number of milk producers has decreased from around 200,000 to 60,000. At the same time, according to the President of the National Council of Agricultural Chambers, the volume of production is not decreasing. Thus, despite the fact that at the level of the CAP it is declared to aim for dispersed production, in fact industrial breeding is gaining in importance, which can be seen especially in pig production. This phenomenon was assessed negatively, and reversing this trend was identified as one of the challenges of the new CAP.

In discussing the Polish strategic plan, the discussants emphasised that the conditions for obtaining financial aid, as well as the related reporting, are becoming increasingly complicated. Such a situation requires the development of agricultural advisory services, in particular state advisory services geared towards individual farm production planning. As Wiktor Szmulewicz stressed, when advice is provided by private entities, they often charge disproportionately high fees for their services.

The subject of the second session, moderated by Professor UJ Dr. hab. Paweł Blajer, was the Polish perspective on the new CAP (National Strategic Plan) and its challenges. In the context of support for animal welfare, Joanna Czaplą (Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development) emphasised that the new CAP targeted support to small and medium-sized farms, in particular for livestock production, as it is livestock farmers who bear the greatest costs of adapting to the EU's new environmental and climate requirements.

Thereafter representatives of Polish public authorities responsible for the support for the agriculture have spoken about the Polish National Strategic Plan of the CAP. Dr. Waldemar Guba has discussed the EU support related to the association of agricultural producers, food supply chains, Mrs. Marzena Skąpska MA and Mr Jarosław Wiśniewski MA EU elaborated on the details concerning Polish public support related to renewable energy in 2023-2027 (agricultural producers, energy cooperatives). Mr. Bogdan Pomianek MA, brought the audience closer to the EU support addressed to young farmers, investments in farms and others included in the National Strategic Plan of the CAP.

During the second part of the session, representatives of Polish agricultural law and economy researchers presented their insights on the subject of the Conference. At first Professor UW Dr hab. Adam Niewiadomski (University of Warsaw), presented a topic: Planning aspects in the CAP National Strategic Plan and other European funds. Then Prof. UAM Dr. hab. Aneta Suchoń, (University of Adam Mickiewicz, Poznań) presented in detail the aspects concerning significant terms and their definitions in the new EU regulations CAP 2023-2027, the National Strategic Plan and Polish legal acts related to the CAP and their impact on practice (including agricultural activity, professionally active farmers, new farmers, young farmers, eligible hectares, processing of agricultural products).

Consequently, Dr. Agata Niewiadomska (University of Warsaw), presented the role of smart villages in the National Strategic Plan of the CAP, Dr. Paweł Popardowski (Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw) expressed his comments on competition rules in the legislation of the European Union after 2022.

At the end of the session Dr. Małgorzata Szymańska (UMCS, Lublin) presented how to efficiently manage natural resources in rural areas and Dr. Hanna Spasowska-Czarny, UMCS, Lublin demonstrated how innovative energy sources comply with the European model of agriculture.

During the third session, moderated by Dr. Leticia BOURGES, CEDR papers were presented by academics representing, among others, France, Italy, Spain and Slovenia. At first, Mr. Wolfgang Burtscher, Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development New Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027 shared his insights on the new CAP. Then Professor Irene Canfora (University of Bari, Italy) shared her comments on the Strategic Plan 2023-2027 in Italy and its implementation. Furthermore Professor María Esther Muñiz Espada (University of Valladolid, Spain) expressed how the Strategic Plan 2023-2027 in Spain shall be implemented. Professor Juan Latorre Ruiz (University of Jaén, Spain) has introduced the audience to the sustainable challenge of agriculture in Spain before the application of the new Common Agrarian Policy".

Then, Professor Catherine Del Cont (University of Nantes, France) expressed the insights of the process of the implementation of the Strategic Plan 2023-2027 in France. In turn Prof. Franci Avsec (University of Novo Mesto, Slovenia) presented the implementation process of the Strategic Plan 2023-2027 in Slovenia.

During the next part of the session Mag. iur Hannes Kronaus, General Treasurer of European Council for Rural Law (CEDR) presented information on the Austria's new CAP-Implementation, the Strategic Plan 2023-2027. This presentation was followed by Mag. Adam Nowak Vice President of European Council of Young Farmers (CEJA) expressed his insights of the generational changes in Agriculture in the context of the National strategic plans CAP 2023-2027.

The session has been completed by the presentation of Professor UAM Dr hab. Aneta Suchoń, who presented Polish legal regulations (drafts) introducing the Polish Strategic Plan and Mag. Tomasz Marzec (Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland) with the paper on sustainable production of renewable energy in rural areas in European Union. The Conference was concluded with the discussion.

Although the situation of farmers in each Member State is different (e.g. the average size of a farm in France is 69 ha, while in Poland it is 11,32 ha), some common points could be found. In all countries, farmers are reluctant to accept the expected decline in agricultural production, which is linked to a reduction in treatments such as fertiliser or spray applications. There is also a trend across the EU towards fewer farms, ageing farmers and an exodus of people from rural areas.

Regardless of views on EU climate policy, the participants in the discussion agreed that environmental issues will become increasingly important under the CAP. Among the proposed measures, farmers should choose those that will best help them adapt their activities to changing climatic conditions and develop a common understanding of the elements of the CAP that they consider least relevant.

The main organiser of the Conference was Professor UAM dr hab. Aneta Suchoń, Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Protection Law, Faculty of Law and Administration of the Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland.